

EFFECTIVE WAYS TO ACHIEVE ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN SOLAR PANELS

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Abstract. In the reforms implemented in our country to build a new Uzbekistan, due to the development of entrepreneurship and the increase in the well-being of the population, the demand for electricity has also been steadily increasing. This article delves into the details about effective ways to achieve energy efficiency in solar panels

Keywords: solar panels, solar system, energy resources, country development and development strategy.

Introduction. Alternative energy sources that meet the demand are currently solar powered equipment. This direction is developing very rapidly around the world, especially Uzbekistan is not lagging behind in this regard. As the price of electricity and other resources is rising, many people are becoming interested in solar panels in our country. In particular, according to the 24th goal of the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the continuous supply of electricity to the economy and the active introduction of "Green economy" technologies to all sectors, to increase the

energy efficiency of the economy by 20%, and to achieve this goal by 2026, electricity increasing the production rate by an additional 30 billion kWh to a total of 100 billion kWh, and saving nearly 3 billion cubic meters of natural gas per year in exchange for increasing the share of renewable energy sources to 25% by 2026. In this regard, a number of priority projects regarding the use of alternative energy in economic sectors, social sector facilities and residential areas are being implemented in our country. In particular, in 2021, for the first time, a 100 MW solar photoelectric plant was launched in the Karmana district of the Navoi region. A large solar photoelectric plant with a capacity of 100 megawatts has been put into operation in Nurabad district of Samarkand region. At the moment, the construction of a project with a capacity of 100 MW, designed to produce 360 million kWh of electricity per year and supply more than 110 thousand households with electricity, has started in the Beruni district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. As a result, 106 million cubic meters of natural gas will be saved, and 160,000 tons of harmful gases will be prevented from being released into the atmosphere. With the saved gas, it will be possible to supply 35,000 households with gas for a year. In addition, 2 solar photoelectric plants with a capacity of 220 MW each in Samarkand and Jizzakh regions, 2 wind power plants with a total capacity of 1000 MW in Bukhara region, and solar photoelectric plants with a capacity of 200 MW in Navoi region and 457 MW in Surkhandarya region, 2024 It is planned to build a wind power plant with a capacity of 500 MW in Navoi region. A total of 2,797 MW of electricity will be produced from the total of new capacities to be commissioned. A solar panel consists of solar cells connected in series and parallel. The solar cells are placed inside a housing to protect them from external environmental influences. The structure of solar modules varies depending on the type of solar cells and their application. For example, amorphous silicon solar cells are usually attached to a flexible coating, and when silicon solar cells are used as remote sources, the front is covered with thick glass coatings. The purest silicon is used in the production of monocrystalline solar panels. In appearance, all cells are connected to one system. After cleaning the monocrystal, it takes time for it to solidify. After hardening, it is separated into very thin plates. Such plates are connected to each other with a thin wire

made of an electrode. Compared to amorphous panels, it is more expensive. The reason is that these types of panels are very difficult to manufacture. However, it is also good to choose this type of panels, because the efficiency of these panels is around 20%, which is a very good indicator for solar panels. To get the polycrystal, the silicon wafer is cooled. It is cheaper to manufacture built-in panels than to manufacture monocrystalline panels. Due to this, these panels are also cheaper. The production of these panels also requires less energy, which also affects the price. Why is the efficiency of these standing panels 18% and below? Due to the mixture that appears inside the polycrystal, the useful work coefficient decreases.

There are several ways to load from solar resources

- Unlike other sources of energy, solar energy does not run out. Installing and getting power from a solar panel is a great solution for using electricity and heat. According to NASA, the sun will not spare our planet for another 6.5 billion years.

- The potential of solar energy is very high. The available energy source for use is measured in terawatts. This is 20 times more than the demand. From it, it is impossible to waste additional solar energy, so this energy can be easily sent to the next generation.

- The sun's rays reach as far as possible from the planet Earth, it does not belong to the buildings around the equator, even at the North Pole, solar energy is easily supplied. Currently, Germany dominates among the countries in terms of cargo transportation in this energy.

- Safe for ecology. The currently used energy sources cannot be effectively replaced without harming the environment. Solar energy is an exception. Production of solar panels, use of it for export ecology.

- No noise. It is completely absent in production and output.

- Savings. Low cost to use.

- There are many fronts that can be used.

Results. On January 23 of this year, on the basis of the President's order, under the chairmanship of the Prime Minister, at the meeting of the video selector dedicated to the discussion of the tasks that should be carried out in the ongoing anomalous cold

weather conditions in Uzbekistan, special attention was paid to increasing the volume of alternative energy production, and the necessary tasks were defined. , indicates that he will continue to march boldly. After all, at the meeting, the officials of the Ministry of Energy and "Uzbekistan National Electric Networks" JSC were assigned the task of going to China for a period of two weeks, completing negotiations with Chinese partners on the construction of 2 gigawatt solar photoelectric plants, and submitting the corresponding draft decision to the Cabinet of Ministers by February 15. Of course, it is not without reason that cooperation relations have been established with representatives of China in the same direction. Because China is the largest producer of solar energy in the world. In the first six months of 2022, 30.88 gigawatts of solar photovoltaic systems were installed in this country. China is also the largest producer of solar equipment. Since 2011, the country has invested more than \$50 billion in new photovoltaic systems. This number is ten times more than the amount invested in the same sector by the entire continent of Europe.

In general, China's share of all stages of solar panel production in the world exceeds 80 percent. In addition, the country plans to generate 33 percent of its electricity from renewable energy sources by 2025. Also, the country's government announced a plan to obtain 1,200 gigawatts of solar and wind energy by 2030. The work that has been done up to now, is currently taking place and is planned in this regard is good, of course. The weight of these works, the final result of the implemented projects will undoubtedly serve the stability of the energy system of our country. But one thing should not be forgotten, as we mentioned above, the demand for electricity is constantly increasing in accordance with the volume of electricity production. Therefore, on June 10, 2022, special attention was paid to it at the meeting of the video selector on the measures of wide use of renewable energy sources in economic sectors, population and social objects. In particular, it was noted that at present there is an additional demand of the population for at least 2-3 billion kWh of electricity, and in the next five years this need will increase by another 10 billion kWh. In such a situation, the most effective way is to increase the use of alternative and renewable energy resources. Uzbekistan is a beautiful country where the sun shines

almost every day of the year. This provides a great natural opportunity for the alternative we are talking about, including solar energy. The effect of converting light into electricity was discovered in 1839 by the French physicist Alexandre Edmond Becquerel. Later, scientists began using selenium to convert light into electricity. The first prototypes of solar panels were founded in 1912 by the Italian photo-chemist Giacomo Luigi Chamichan. In 1954, Bell Laboratories announced the creation of the first silicon-based solar panel. But the efficiency of this solar cell was only 6 percent.

Discussion. Today, a grid-connected solar panel system can provide a home with full power for just a few hours on average. Even if the power goes out, the batteries will continue to work. The operation of solar panels is based on the principle of converting special substances into electricity. In particular, two silicon wafers are coated with various substances that generate free electrons, mainly boron and phosphorus. Under the influence of sunlight, these electrons begin to move and generate an electric current. The generated electricity is then transferred to solar energy harvesting batteries. In general, the effectiveness in this regard is directly related to the number of sunny days compared to cloudy or rainy weather. In Uzbekistan, there are more than 300 sunny days per year on average, which is one of the main factors and advantages of the development of solar electricity. As we mentioned above, the history of obtaining electricity from sunlight goes back almost 200 years, but despite favorable conditions, the use of sunlight came to us much later. In the last 10 years, solar energy has become one of the priority directions in our country. The decree on the further development of alternative energy sources adopted in 2013 was one of the important documents that encouraged the mass use of solar energy. According to experts' calculations, solar power plants can produce a total of 600 billion kilowatt-hours of electricity in Uzbekistan. This is eight times more than the current electricity needs of the country. According to the experts of the Asian Development Bank, the potential of solar energy is about 51 billion tons of oil equivalent. To implement it, our country started using renewable energy sources. It is not only the sun, but also the energy obtained with the help of wind, water currents, biogas plants, etc. In order to introduce and use solar panels in Uzbekistan, a number of measures are being implemented to

encourage residents and entrepreneurs of our country by providing incentives and subsidies.

Conclusion. It can be seen from these that the stability of electric energy, which is directly related to economic development and the well-being of the population, and whose demand is constantly increasing, depends to a large extent on the expansion of the use of renewable energy, including solar energy, both today and in the future. Therefore, most developed and developing countries are giving priority to this issue. According to a report by the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), global solar energy production will increase to a record 179 terawatt-hours in 2021. Growth - 22 percent. This year, global solar generation was 849 gigawatts, which accounted for 3.6 percent of global electricity generation. Currently, the top five solar power producing countries are China (340 gigawatts), USA (102.9 gigawatts), Japan (78.5 gigawatts), Germany (62 gigawatts) and India (57 gigawatts). It is noteworthy that three of the top five countries in this regard are representatives of our continent.

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